

Attitudes of Mindset Towards Foreign Language Learning: Exploring Self-Image, Inhibition, Risk-taking, Ego-Permeability and Ambiguity

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to examine the attitudes of people with diverse mindsets toward foreign language learning, focusing on factors like self-image, inhibition, risk-taking, ego-permeability, and ambiguity. Using mindset theory to distinguish between fixed and growth mindsets, this study investigates how mindset orientations influence individuals' attitudes and behaviours when learning a foreign language. To acquire a full understanding of the relationships between mindsets and these specific attitudes, a mixed-methods approach combining quantitative surveys and qualitative interviews is used. The findings add to the current body of knowledge by throwing light on the function of mindset in foreign language learning and offer insights for educators and language learning practitioners.

Keywords: Mindset, Foreign Language Learning, Attitudes, Self-Image, Inhibition, Risk-Taking, Ego-Permeability, Ambiguity.

1. Introduction:

Learning a foreign language is a complex process that necessitates not only linguistic skills but also a positive mindset and approach toward language learning. Carol Dweck's theory of mindset has acquired popularity in educational settings, particularly language learning environments. A person's mindset refers to their beliefs about the nature of their talents and intelligence, with fixed and growth mindsets indicating two distinct orientations. Individuals with a fixed mindset regard their abilities as fixed traits, whereas those with a growth mindset believe in the possibility of growth via effort and learning (Yeager & Dweck, 2012).

Previous study has demonstrated that mindset orientations have a substantial influence on individuals' attitudes toward learning, academic achievement, and personal growth ("Mindset," 2012). However, more research into the specific attitudes of individuals with varied mindsets toward foreign language learning is required. This study aims to fill this gap by examining the attitudes of people with fixed and growth mindsets toward learning Russian as a foreign language, with a focus on factors such as self-image, inhibition, risk-taking, ego-permeability, and ambiguity (Alavinia & Salmasi, 2012; "Self-Regulation and Risk-Taking," 2012).

The study collected a sample of students studying Russian as a foreign language. Participants were selected from language learning programmes in the universities, and they represented a wide range of backgrounds, and language learning experiences. Surveys and interviews were used to examine participants' mindset orientations, attitudes toward foreign language learning, and related factors such as self-image, inhibition, risk-taking, ego-permeability, and ambiguity.

The collected data will be examined quantitatively and qualitatively. To investigate the links between thinking orientations and attitudes toward foreign language learning, descriptive descriptive analyses will be employed. Thematic analysis of qualitative data from interviews will be used to discover common themes and patterns relating to self-image, inhibition, risk-taking, ego-permeability, and ambiguity.

The study's findings have significance for language educators, curriculum designers, and language learners. Educators can customise instructional strategies and interventions to build positive mindsets and improve language learning results by understanding how mindset orientations influence individuals' attitudes toward foreign language learning. The findings of the study may also contribute to the larger field of mindset research and to the existing literature on foreign language learning process.

The purpose of this study is to examine into to the attitudes of people with various mindsets about learning Russian as a foreign language, focusing on characteristics like self-image, inhibition, risk-taking, ego-permeability, and ambiguity. The study's sample of Russian language learners will provide valuable insights into the significance of mindset in foreign language learning environments. This study aims to contribute to our understanding of how mindset orientations influence foreign language learning results and to guide pedagogical approaches in language education by investigating these attitudes.

2. Attitude towards learning

Individuals' attitudes toward learning have a significant impact on their educational outcomes and personal growth. The concept of mindset, introduced by psychologist Carol Dweck, is one famous theory that has received significant attention in this context. Mindset relates to an individual's beliefs about the nature of intelligence and abilities, with fixed and development mindsets being distinguished. Individuals who have a fixed mindset feel that their abilities are innate and unchangeable, whereas those who have a growth mindset believe that abilities may be developed through work and learning (Dweck, 2006).

According to research, mindset orientations have a significant influence on individuals' attitudes toward learning, academic achievement, and overall personal growth. Individuals that have a growth mindset welcome challenge, persevere in the face of difficulties, and see failures as chances for learning and improvement (Alavinia & Salmasi, 2012; Kormos et al., 2011a; Tanaka et al., 2002). They believe that with practise and effort, intelligence and abilities can be developed. Individuals with a fixed mindset, on the other hand, generally avoid problems, avoid effort, and feel discouraged by setbacks. They frequently feel that intelligence is a fixed characteristic and that failure indicates their innate limitations (Blackwell, Trzesniewski, & Dweck, 2007).

While numerous studies have looked at the impact of mindset on learning outcomes (Gardner et al., 1985; Kormos et al., 2011; Macintyre & Charos, 1996; Metcalfe & Metcalfe, 1981; Porkaew, 2004)., there is still a need for more research into the specific attitudes of people with fixed and growth mindsets toward learning, particularly in terms of self-image, inhibition, risk-taking, ego-permeability, and ambiguity. These attitudes have a direct impact on learning outcomes and behaviours.

Understanding how these attitudes are related to mindset orientations can provide significant information about the underlying processes that govern learning behaviours and shape educational strategies. Individuals who have a favourable self-image of learning, for example, are more likely to be motivated and involved in their educational efforts. Learning and progress can be hampered by inhibition, or the inclination to hold back and avoid taking chances. Risk-taking and a willingness to venture outside one's comfort zone, on the other hand, are related with better learning and adaptability. Ego-permeability is the willingness to receive feedback and alter one's views and strategies in order to progress. Ambiguity tolerance, or the ability to cope with ambiguous and complex situations, is crucial in problem solving and critical thinking (Yeager & Dweck, 2012).

The importance of these learning attitudes in educational contexts cannot be overstated. Students' attitudes about learning influence their motivation, engagement, and readiness to tackle challenging work. Their resilience, problem-solving abilities, and adaptability in the face of uncertainty and ambiguity are also influenced by these mindsets. Recognizing the significance of encouraging positive attitudes toward learning, educators, parents, and policymakers can use this knowledge to establish interventions and supportive environments that encourage growth mindsets and improve educational outcomes.

As a result, the goal of this study is to examine into the attitudes of people with fixed and growth mindsets toward learning, with a particular emphasis on self-image, inhibition, risk-taking, ego-permeability, and ambiguity. This study attempts to provide a full knowledge of how thinking orientations impact these attitudes by using a mixed-methods approach that combines quantitative surveys and qualitative interviews. The outcomes of this study will add to the existing body of knowledge on the function of mindset in shaping learning habits, influencing educational strategies and interventions aimed at cultivating positive attitudes toward learning.

The following is the structure of this research: The part that follows will provide an overview of the literature on mindset theory, its impact on learning attitudes. The methodology, including participant selection, data collecting, and analysis procedures, will be covered in the next section. The findings will be presented in the results section, followed implications, limits, and future directions. Finally, the article will finish with a summary of the important findings and their implications for encouraging good attitudes toward learning.

3. Methodology:

3.1 *Participants:* Participants who were learning Russian as foreign language were selected as sample to find out their attitudes toward learning using questionnaire (Appendix- 2).

3.2 *Measures:* The participants' mindset will be assessed using the Mindset Assessment Scale and questionnaire appendix-1 (Dweck, 2006,), a validated self-report measure that captures individuals' beliefs about the malleability of intelligence and abilities.

3.3 *Attitudes towards learning will be examined:*

- *Self-Image:* Harter (1982) explored what self-image is and how it affects one's understanding of oneself and how it impacts academic ability and achievement.
- *Inhibition:* Watson and Clark (1991) used the inhibition scale to assess shyness and avoidance in learning. Avoidance and shyness are characteristics of the fixed mindset, which is poor at motivating and learning.
- *Risk-taking:* Risk-taking in a certain domain becomes critical in the context of learning. Weber et al. (2006) assessed participants' readiness to take risks in the context of learning using the Domain-Specific Risk-Taking Scale.
- *Ego-Permeability:* Ego-Permeability is an important aspect that influences an individual's overall performance. The Ego-Permeability Scale was used by Koestner and McClelland (1992) to assess participants' openness to feedback and willingness to adjust their self-concept depending on new knowledge.
- *Ambiguity:* In learning situation specially in foreign language, students face ambiguity situation in linguistic concepts; it is important to overcome the ambiguity to carry on learning. Budner (1962) utilized the Tolerance for Ambiguity Scale to measure participants' comfort level in dealing with ambiguous learning situations.

3.4 *Procedure:* The study will use a mixed-methods approach. First, participants will complete a mindset evaluation and assessments of attitudes toward learning. In a learning environment, particularly in a foreign language, students experience ambiguity in linguistic concepts; it is necessary to overcome the ambiguity in order to continue learning. Budner (1962) used the Tolerance for Ambiguity Scale to assess participants' level of comfort in dealing with confusing learning circumstances. The survey results will be quantitatively examined to compare the attitudes of students with fixed and growth mindsets. Secondly, The interviews will be examined in terms of attitudes toward learning.

4. Results:

Mindset and Attitude analysis

Attitude	Fixed Mindset		Growth Mindset
Self-Image	38	>	34
Inhibition (shyness)	34	>	22
Risk-taking	38	<	44.5
Ego-Permeability	39	>	35
Ambiguity (Tolerance)	42.5	<	44.5

[1]

Data about the mindset of the student who were learning Russian language were obtained. The participants' attitude about foreign language learning were recorded. The questionnaire had five sets of attitudes: Self-Image, Inhibition, Risk-taking, Ego-Permeability, and Ambiguity are the attitudes towards foreign language learning.

Students with a fixed mindset were reported a tendency to develop a strong self-image in learning and making mistakes. They tend to be more shy or uncomfortable. Fixed mindsets avoided challenges. They were less capable of dealing with ambiguity. whereas students with growth mindset were concerned for their self-image less self-conscious. They were more daring in their approach. They were better equipped to deal with ambiguity [1].

[2]

In language learning, fixed mindset students tended to have a strong self-image. They were more shy or uncomfortable, which prevented them from expressing their views or feelings. It reduced involvement, which hindered language learning and proper response. Fixed mindsets had a poor risk-taking attitude, which restricted their willingness to put up effort and challenge in learning. These are essential components of foreign language learning. They had lower ambiguity bearing capacities, whereas growth mindset had the reverse attitude. Growth

mindsets exhibited less self-image behaviour when it came to foreign language learning, therefore making mistakes and learning came naturally to them. Because they were less shy, they participated in the classroom for linguistic development. They took more risks, putting in more effort and trying new strategies to learn and recall linguistic facts and word meanings. These mindsets appeared more suitable for learning a foreign language. Because they were less self centred, they embraced advice, recommendations, and guidance, as well as praises and feedback following failures. They took them positively for self-motivation and were better equipped to deal with ambiguity. As result of the survey results, both mindsets had different attitudes regarding foreign language learning. Growth mindset attitudes were better suited to the behaviour required by foreign language learning; fixed mindset attitudes trailed in this competition [1][2].

Interview analysis

The responses of both types of students fixed mindset and growth mindset in the classroom throughout the course were recorded and analyzed. Students with fixed mindset participated less in class after getting a wrong answer and failure, but growth mindset students continued to learn and participate in class even after failing. After attempting the incorrect attempt, igrowth mindset used a different approach to understand the fact, and some even used other strategies to recall the grammatical structure. Students with a growth mindset participated more frequently, even after experiencing failure; they increased their efforts to achieve the goal.

They remained motivated throughout the course. Students with a growth mindset performed better in the exam. Difficulty is a frequent thing for students who are learning a foreign language. This challenge can be found in grammatical construction, pronunciation, meaning, and usage. It's ambiguous and usually surprisingly subtle. Students with fixed mindsets performed better only when they did not fail.

5. Findings corresponds with existing research

Carol Dweck's mindset theory distinguishes between two major mindsets: fixed mindset and growth mindset. Individuals' beliefs and assumptions regarding the nature of skills and intelligence are represented by these mindsets.

The assumption that one's abilities are fixed and unchangeable is referred to as a fixed mindset (Dweck, 2006). Individuals with a fixed mindset believe that their intelligence and talents are predetermined traits, and that they have little room for growth and progress. Failures and setbacks are interpreted as indicators of their innate limitations, resulting to feelings of helplessness and discouragement. Growth mindset, on the other hand, represents the belief that abilities may be developed through effort, study, and perseverance (Dweck, 2006). Challenges and barriers are regarded as chances for growth and learning by people who have a growth mindset. They believe that intelligence and skills can be developed, which leads to a motivation

for constant growth and a readiness to put up effort in their learning efforts. Significant research has been conducted on the relationship between mindset and learning attitudes, including self-image, inhibition, risk-taking, ego-permeability, and ambiguity (Alavinia & Salmasi, 2012).

Self-image is important in developing attitudes. When it comes to learning, those with a fixed mindset may have a fragile self-image. They are more prone to associate their self-worth with their ability and may be afraid of failure, which limits their willingness to take on difficult tasks. Individuals with a growth mindset, on the other hand, tend to have a more resilient self-image, perceiving mistakes and failures as opportunities for learning and growth (Blackwell, Trzesniewski, & Dweck, 2007).

Inhibition is the inclination to hold back and avoid taking risks when learning. Individuals with a fixed mindset may be more likely to demonstrate inhibition as a result of their fear of failure and desire to avoid tough situations that may harm their self-image. Individuals with a growth mindset, on the other hand, are more likely to welcome challenges and accept risks, recognizing them as chances for learning and improvement (Blackwell et al., 2007).

The willingness to move outside one's comfort zone and try new ideas or strategies in learning is closely tied to risk-taking. Individuals with a growth mindset are more likely to take chances and attempt new things because they believe in the potential for growth via experimentation and learning from mistakes (Yeager & Dweck, 2012).

The openness to hearing feedback, modifying beliefs, and adapting strategies in response to new information is referred to as ego-permeability. Individuals with a growth mindset have higher degrees of ego-permeability because they view feedback as valuable information for growth and improvement (Yeager & Dweck, 2012).

Ambiguity tolerance, or being at ease in unclear and complex situations, is essential for problem solving and critical thinking. Individuals with a growth mindset are frequently more at ease with ambiguity because they see it as an opportunity to explore new options and learn from uncertainty (Yeager & Dweck, 2012).

Existing research has consistently shown that mindset has an impact on learning attitudes. Individuals with a growth mindset have more positive attitudes toward learning, such as adaptable self-image, reduced inhibition, greater risk-taking proclivity, increased ego-permeability, and greater comfort with ambiguity, according to research (Blackwell et al., 2007; Yeager & Dweck, 2012). These attitudes contribute to increased motivation, engagement, and resilience in the face of difficulty, which leads to better learning outcomes.

6. Attitudes Associated with Fixed Mindset

Individuals with a fixed mindset have specific attitudes that shape their behaviour and learning processes. Their belief that abilities and intelligence are fixed features influences

their attitudes, resulting in distinct patterns of self-image, inhibition, risk-taking, ego-permeability, and ambiguity tolerance.

Self-Image:

A negative self-image is typical among those who have a fixed mindset. They have a tendency to see their abilities as limited and fixed, which leads to reduced self-esteem and self-confidence in learning situations (Dweck, 2006). Individuals with a fixed mindset may be afraid of failure because it undermines their self-image and reinforces their ideas about innate limitations. This unfavourable self-image can undermine their motivation and readiness to take on difficult tasks.

Inhibition:

When faced with new or tasks that may expose their perceived limitations, people with fixed mindsets frequently demonstrate inhibition. They avoid circumstances that may necessitate great effort or result in failure (Dweck, 2006). Fear of failure, as well as a need to preserve a favourable self-image, can contribute to their proclivity to avoid risks and adhere to familiar and safe tasks. This limitation limits their development and learning opportunities.

Risk-Taking:

Individuals with a fixed mindset are often risk-averse due to their fears of failure and negative judgments. They tend to stay in their comfort zones and avoid risk-taking that may include ambiguity or potential setbacks (Dweck, 2006). This fear of taking risks limits their exposure to new experiences and opportunities for growth, limiting their ability to broaden their skills and knowledge.

Ego-Permeability:

Individuals with fixed mindsets frequently suffer with ego-permeability, which relates to their willingness to taking feedback and changing their beliefs and strategies. They may be resistant to input that questions their self-image and intelligence, viewing it as a threat (Dweck, 2006). This resistance to feedback limits their ability to reflect on and learn from their mistakes, limiting both their personal and academic achievement.

Ambiguity:

Individuals who have a fixed mindset are less tolerant of ambiguity and uncertainty. They prefer jobs that are straightforward and well-defined over ones that involve complexity and ambiguity (Dweck, 2006). The fixed mindset's fear of ambiguity might impede their ability to think critically, solve problems, and adapt to unfamiliar or ambiguous situations.

The association between a fixed mindset and the preceding attitudes is supported by empirical research. A study conducted by Blackwell, Trzesniewski, and Dweck (2007) discovered that students with a fixed mindset were more likely to have a negative self-image and avoid difficulties than those with a growth mindset. Similarly, Yeager and Dweck (2012) discovered that students with fixed mindsets were less inclined to take risks and be open to criticism, resulting in poor academic achievement.

In the context of learning, a fixed mindset has a negative impact on self-image, inhibition, risk-taking, ego-permeability, and ambiguity tolerance. Individuals' progress is impeded by these attitudes, as are their abilities to overcome problems and their motivation to engage in learning activities. Recognizing and addressing fixed mindset tendencies can assist individuals in developing a more adaptable and growth-oriented mindset, hence fostering academic and personal development.

7. Attitudes Associated with Growth Mindset

People that have a growth mindset have specific attitudes that influence their learning behaviours and approaches. These attitudes, which are based on the belief that abilities and intelligence can be grown via hard work and learning, have a major impact on self-image, inhibition, risk-taking, ego-permeability, and ambiguity tolerance in the context of learning (Atwood, 2010; Chase, 2010; Havard, 2007; Malherbe & Stanz, 2012; Sochan, 2012; Yeager & Dweck, 2012).

Self-Image:

A positive self-image is one of the key attitudes typically found among people with a growth mindset. They see their abilities as changeable and have confidence in the ability to grow and improve (Dweck, 2006). This positive self-image boosts their self-esteem and confidence, allowing them to face obstacles with optimism and resilience. Individuals with a growth mindset see failures as chances for learning and are more inclined to persevere in the face of difficulty.

Inhibition:

Individuals with a growth mindset had fewer levels of inhibition than those with a fixed mindset. They are more willing to take on difficult work and welcome opportunities for advancement (Dweck, 2006). Individuals with a growth mindset view problems as opportunities for growth rather than threats to their self-image. They are less inclined to avoid tasks due to fear of failure and are more willing to expand their boundaries and expand their capabilities.

Risk-Taking:

Individuals with a growth mindset are more inclined to take risks in their learning attempts. They understand that taking risks is an important element of the learning process and an opportunity for personal improvement (Dweck, 2006). They are more likely to push outside of their comfort zones, attempt new approaches, and explore uncharted ground. This risk-taking attitude exposes them to new experiences, encourages learning, and fosters resilience in the face of disappointments.

Ego-Permeability:

Individuals with a growth mindset have higher degrees of ego-permeability, which relates to their openness to taking feedback and modifying their beliefs and strategies (Yeager & Dweck, 2012). They see comments as vital information that can help them learn and grow. They regard feedback as a chance for growth and improvement rather than a threat to their self-image. Because they are open to feedback, they may incorporate constructive criticism, learn from their mistakes, and improve their approaches.

Ambiguity:

Individuals with a growth mindset are more tolerant of ambiguity and uncertainty. They are more at ease in dealing with complex and ambiguous situations (Dweck, 2006). Individuals with a growth mindset welcomes difficulties that involve uncertainty, viewing them as opportunities to improve problem-solving and critical thinking skills. Their openness to ambiguity allows individuals to navigate varied learning contexts and adapt to new situations.

The association between a growth mindset and these attitudes is supported by empirical research. According to a study conducted by Blackwell, Trzesniewski, and Dweck (2007), students with a growth mindset had better levels of self-confidence and were more inclined to welcome difficulties than those with a fixed mindset. Furthermore, Yeager and Dweck (2012) discovered that students with a growth mindset were more willing to take academic risks and were more open to criticism for development.

Finally, in the context of learning, a growth mindset influences individuals' attitudes toward self-image, inhibition, risk-taking, ego-permeability, and ambiguity. These attitudes foster resilience, motivation, and a proactive approach to overcoming obstacles. Individuals can create a more adaptive and growth-oriented perspective by cultivating a growth mindset, hence improving their learning outcomes and personal development.

8. Implications for Educational Practices

Mindset and attitudes toward learning have significant implications for educational approaches. Recognizing the role of mindset in affecting learning behaviours and results, educators and policymakers can use strategies and interventions to promote a growth

mindset and positive learning attitudes. Cultivating a growth mindset has the ability to improve educational outcomes and help students develop overall.

Emphasize Effort and Growth:

Educators should focus on the importance of persistence and growth in the learning process. Students can be taught to adopt a growth mindset by emphasising that intelligence and abilities can be increased through effort and practise (Dweck, 2006). Instead of focusing simply on outcomes, praising pupils' effort and development can foster a belief in the worth of hard work and resilience.

Provide Constructive Feedback:

Feedback is critical in building a growth mindset. Educators should provide timely and constructive feedback that encourages students to view mistakes as chances to improve (Yeager & Dweck, 2012). Feedback should emphasise effort, strategies, and places for progress rather than the final result. This teaches children that setbacks are temporary and can be overcome through study and effort.

Cultivate a Safe and Supportive Learning Environment:

It is critical to foster a growth mindset by providing a safe and supportive learning environment. Educators should foster a learning environment that stimulates experimentation, cooperation, and open dialogue (Dweck, 2006). Giving students opportunity to share their ideas, learn from one another, and embrace challenges develops a growth-oriented mindset and good learning attitudes.

Teach Metacognitive Strategies:

Metacognitive methods can help students become more conscious of their own learning processes and build a growth mindset. Teachers can teach students to evaluate their learning strategies, create goals, and track their progress (Yeager & Dweck, 2012). Encouraging students to identify and adjust their techniques in response to feedback and self-reflection fosters a sense of empowerment and confidence in their potential to develop.

Encourage Mastery-oriented Tasks and Learning Goals:

Learning activities that emphasise mastery-oriented tasks and learning goals might help to foster a growth attitude. Educators should give kids opportunity to participate in challenging and meaningful tasks involving effort and skill development (Dweck, 2006). Focusing on the learning experience rather of grades or comparisons with others encourages students to appreciate growth and knowledge.

Supportive Parent and Family Involvement:

Parental participation is crucial in building a growth mindset. Educators can engage parents and families by providing strategies for encouraging a growth mindset at home and giving tools for parents to assist their children's learning journey (Yeager & Dweck, 2012). Collaborating with parents as educational partners can help to reinforce growth mindset concepts and behaviours in a variety of contexts.

These strategies and interventions are designed to foster a growth mindset and positive learning attitudes. Educational approaches can enable children to accept challenges, persevere in the face of setbacks, and acquire a lifetime love of learning by cultivating a belief in the possibilities for growth, effort, and resilience.

9. Conclusion

This research examined at how people with fixed and growth mindsets approach foreign language learning, focusing on self-image, inhibition, risk-taking, ego-permeability, and ambiguity. The findings extend on the distinct attitudes associated with these mindsets, as well as the implications for language learning.

The study found that students with a fixed mindset had a strong preference for self-image in language learning. They were shy and apprehensive, which limited their ability to convey their thoughts and feelings. This decreased their participation and hampered their language learning and automatic response. Furthermore, fixed mindset students had poor risk-taking attitudes, which hindered their desire to put up effort and face problems in their learning, both of which are critical components in foreign language acquisition. They also exhibited egoistic inclinations, as they were less responsive to advice, suggestions, and feedback following failures. Furthermore, their ability to deal with ambiguity was worse than that of people with a growth mentality.

Growth mindset pupils, on the other hand, demonstrated attitudes more suited to foreign language learning. They exhibited less self-image behaviour, accepting mistakes as natural and viewing them as learning opportunities. They were less shy, allowing for active engagement in the classroom and supporting linguistic growth. They were more likely to take risks, put in more effort, and try new strategies to learn and remember linguistic facts and meanings. They also demonstrated a more open approach, receiving feedback and guidance and using failure as a source of self-motivation. Their better ability to deal with ambiguity was also noticeable.

According to the survey data, fixed and growth mindsets exhibit different attitudes toward foreign language learning, with growth mindset attitudes aligning more closely with the needs of foreign language learning. This was corroborated by both types of students' responses throughout the course, where growth mindset students maintained their participation and motivation even after setbacks, ultimately attaining better exam results. Students with a fixed mindset, on the other hand, fared better only when they did not encounter failure.

Classroom teaching designs can be modified to foster positive attitudes and address mindset-related concerns. Reduced cognitive load and the use of multimedia techniques can improve sensory learning and comprehension in students with both fixed and growth mindsets. Furthermore, delivering appropriate praise that encourages practise, effort, and dedication might have an indirect influence on mindset transformation in the classroom. Students' mindsets can be effectively altered through training on the malleability of the brain and intelligence, supporting a growth-oriented perspective. Implementing instructional strategies that emphasise repetition, effort, and the use of various learning strategies can help students develop a growth mindset.

This study emphasises the need of cultivating a growth mindset in foreign language learning. Educators may establish an environment that supports resilience, risk-taking, and openness to feedback by addressing mindset-related attitudes, thereby improving educational outcomes and student performance in foreign language learning.

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You have a certain amount of intelligence, and you can't really do much to change it.

Strongly Agree	Agree	Mostly Agree	Mostly Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
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Your intelligence is something about you that you can't change very much.

Strongly Agree	Agree	Mostly Agree	Mostly Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
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No matter who you are, you can significantly change your intelligence level.

Strongly Agree	Agree	Mostly Agree	Mostly Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
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To be honest, you can't really change how intelligent you are.

Strongly Agree	Agree	Mostly Agree	Mostly Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
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You can always substantially change how intelligent you are.

Strongly Agree	Agree	Mostly Agree	Mostly Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
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You can learn new things, but you can't really change your basic intelligence

Strongly Agree	Agree	Mostly Agree	Mostly Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
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No matter how much intelligence you have, you can always change it quite a bit.

Strongly Agree	Agree	Mostly Agree	Mostly Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
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You can change even your basic intelligence level considerably.

Strongly Agree	Agree	Mostly Agree	Mostly Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
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You have a certain amount of talent, and you can't really do much to change it.

Strongly Agree	Agree	Mostly Agree	Mostly Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Your talent in an area is something about you that you can't change very much.					
Strongly Agree	Agree	Mostly Agree	Mostly Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
No matter who you are, you can significantly change your level of talent.					
Strongly Agree	Agree	Mostly Agree	Mostly Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
To be honest, you can't really change how much talent you have.					
Strongly Agree	Agree	Mostly Agree	Mostly Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
You can always substantially change how much talent you have.					
Strongly Agree	Agree	Mostly Agree	Mostly Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
You can learn new things, but you can't really change your basic level of talent.					
Strongly Agree	Agree	Mostly Agree	Mostly Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
No matter how much talent you have, you can always change it quite a bit.					
Strongly Agree	Agree	Mostly Agree	Mostly Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
You can change even your basic level of talent considerably.					
Strongly Agree	Agree	Mostly Agree	Mostly Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree

Appendix -2

Language Learning Attitudes Questionnaire

Fill out the following questionnaire, checking the box which best describes whether you agree or disagree with each statement. This is for yourself not for anyone else, so answer as honestly as you can.

SA= Strongly Agree, **A**= Agree, **N**= Neither agree nor disagree, **D**= Disagree, **SD**= Strongly Disagree

	SA	A	N	D	SD
1. I think I'm a pretty good language learner.	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____
2. Learning a language may be important to my goals, but I don't expect it to be much fun.	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____
3. My language learning aptitude is probably pretty high.	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____
4. I don't have any idea about how to go about learning a language.	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____
5. I think that I could learn pretty much any language I really put my mind to, given the right circumstances.	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____
6. I worry a lot about making mistakes.	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____
7. I'm afraid people will laugh at me if I don't say things right.	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____
8. I end up trembling and practically in a cold sweat when I have to talk in front of people.	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____
9. I find it hard to make conversation even with people who speak my own language.	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____

	SA	A	N	D	SD
10. I feel a resistance from within when I try to speak in a foreign language, even if I've practiced.	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____
11. It is a mark of respect to people to learn their language if you're living in their country.	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____
12. I like getting to know people from other countries, in general.	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____
13. Speaking the language of the community where I'll be living will let me help people more than I could otherwise.	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____
14. I don't like the idea of relying on speaking English (or my mother tongue) in another country.	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____
15. I think the people of the country where I'll be living would like for me to learn their language.	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____
16. I won't really be able to get to know people well if I don't speak their language.	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____
17. There is a right and a wrong way to do almost everything, and I think it's my duty to figure out which is which and do it right.	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____
18. It annoys me when people don't give me a clear-cut answer, but just beat around the bush.	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____
19. You should say "yes" if you mean yes and "no" if you mean no. Not to do so is dishonest.	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____

	SA	A	N	D	SD
20. You have to understand people's culture and value system before you can be sure whether some things are right or wrong.	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____
21. I like to mimic other accents, and people say I do it well.	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____
22. I can do impersonations of famous people.	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____
23. I find it easy to "put myself in other people's shoes" and imagine how they feel.	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____
24. In school, if I didn't know an answer for sure, I'd sometimes answer out loud in class anyway.	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____
25. I often think out loud, trying out my ideas on other people.	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____
26. I want to have everything worked out in my own head before I answer.	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____
27. I'd call myself a risk-taker	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____